

**SURFACE CHARACTERISATION OF KEVLAR
BY INVERSE GAS CHROMATOGRAPHY**

P. J. C. Chappell
Polymer Research Group,
Materials Research Laboratories,
Maribyrnong, Victoria 3032,
AUSTRALIA

and

D. R. Williams
Department of Chemical Engineering,
Imperial College,
Prince Consort Road,
Kensington, London SW7 2BY,
UK

ABSTRACT

The surface thermodynamic properties of Kevlar fibres have been determined using Inverse Gas Chromatography (IGC). This is a simple gas adsorption technique in which the fibres are used as the stationary phase in a gas chromatographic column. Fundamental thermodynamic information for a series of commercial Kevlar 49 and Kevlar 29 materials is reported. The technique is shown to be reliable and sensitive to the presence of surface contaminants on the fibres, and the results can therefore be used to gauge the thermodynamic cleanliness of the fibre materials. This information is important for understanding the fundamentals of fibre-matrix adhesion and in quantifying fibre cleanliness for quality assurance in critical composite fabrication.

INTRODUCTION

The mechanical properties of composites depend upon the bulk properties of the fibre and resin phases, as well as the interactions between the two phases. These interactions take place not only at the fibre-resin interface, but also in a complex interphase region comprising the outer layers of the fibre, fibre surface contaminants, resin impurities and voids which have migrated to the interface, and resin adjacent to the interface which is different from the bulk.

Because little is known about the interphase region and the way it affects composite performance, surface characterisation of fibres is of interest from both theoretical and practical standpoints. This information will be important in the future design and manufacture of advanced composite materials.

Surface spectroscopic techniques such as Auger Electron and X-Ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy are routinely used for surface analysis, and yield information about the presence of chemical entities. However, in order to obtain information about the chemical activity of fibre surfaces it is necessary to use techniques involving interaction of matter, rather than radiation, with the surface. A promising technique for obtaining thermodynamic information on fibre surfaces is gas adsorption using Inverse Gas Chromatography (IGC) [1,2]. Simple modifications to a commercial gas chromatograph allow accurate IGC measurements to be made on fibres taken from roving or fabric.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Analytical gas chromatography relies on differences between solid-vapour interactions to separate unknown vapours injected into a carrier gas stream flowing through a column lined or packed with a standard stationary phase. The same principle can be used to give information about an unknown solid surface by using the vapours of specific pure liquids. This is the basis of IGC. A chromatographic column is packed with fibres taken from roving or fabric, and the vapour is injected into the carrier gas passing through the column. As the vapour molecules are carried along the column they are adsorbed onto and desorbed from the fibres under equilibrium conditions. The vapour molecules are detected at the outlet of the column and the gas chromatograph detector measures the concentration profile as a function of time from the moment of injection, as shown in Figure 1.

The samples of Kevlar used in this study were dried in situ prior to use and are listed in Table 1. Solvent cleaned samples were Soxhlet extracted successively with water, acetone, dichloromethane and hexane. Hexane, heptane, octane, nonane and decane (all greater than 99% purity), were injected as vapours into a 1m x 1/4" stainless steel column packed to about 30%, by volume, with Kevlar. The column was installed in a Varian model 1400 gas chromatograph equipped with a flame ionization detector.

- A- Helium carrier gas B- Flow transducer and control valve
 C- Pressure Transducer D- Vapour injection port
 E- Temperature Bath F- Fibre filled GC column
 G- GC detector H- Analogue detector output
 J- Computer ———> - Direction of carrier gas flow

Figure 1. Schematic diagram of inverse gas chromatographic apparatus.

TABLE 1

Description of Kevlar Samples

Sample Number	Description	Sample Preparation
1	Kevlar 49 Roving Type 968	Dried
2	Kevlar 49 Roving Type 968	Solvent extracted
3	Kevlar 49 Fabric Type 353 Style CS800* (scoured)	Dried
4	Kevlar 29 Fabric Type 755 Style CS816 (vinyl-ester compatible finish)	Dried
5	Kevlar 29 Fabric Type 755 Style CS800 (scoured)	Dried
6	Kevlar 29 Fabric Type 755 Style CS800 (scoured)	Solvent extracted

* CS denotes Clark Schwebel woven material.

The carrier gas used was ultra-high purity helium at a flow rate of 10 standard cubic centimetres per minute. The flow rate was controlled by a precision metering valve and measured by a thermal conductivity mass flow transducer. A differential pressure transducer was used to measure the carrier gas pressure at the point of vapour injection. Temperature control was achieved by enclosing the column in a jacket through which water was circulated from a precision thermostatic bath. Chromatograms were recorded digitally on a computerised multi-channel analyser at temperatures of 20, 30, 40 and 50 C.

Analysis of IGC data is based on the retention time t_R between injection and detection of the peak maximum. This quantity includes the gas holdup time t_M which is the time taken for the vapour molecules to travel through the column without interacting with the fibres. The quantities t_R and t_M are illustrated in Figure 2. Both t_R and t_M can be related via the carrier gas flow rate to volumes, known as the retention volume V_R and dead volume V_M , respectively.

Figure 2. Chromatograms for methane (1), hexane (2), heptane (3), and octane (4) on sample 1, showing gas holdup time t_M and retention time t_R .

The dead volume is calculated from the retention time of an inert (non-adsorbing) gas, usually methane, injected into the column. The difference between V_R for an adsorbing probe and V_M , corrected for column pressure gradient (j), adsorption onto the column walls (V_W) and column temperature T relative to 273.15 K, is known as the nett retention volume V_N .

$$V_N = j \cdot t_R \cdot F \cdot (T/273.15) - V_M - V_W \quad (1)$$

By measuring V_N as a function of temperature it is possible to calculate the isosteric heat q_d , entropy ΔS_A^0 and free energy ΔG_A^0 of adsorption for a given vapour for a solid with specific surface area A [3,4].

$$q_d = R \cdot d(\ln V_N) / d(1/T) \quad (2)$$

$$\Delta G_A^0 = -R \cdot T \cdot \ln(V_N \cdot p_{s,g} / A \cdot \pi_s) \quad (3)$$

$$\Delta S_A^0 = -(q_d + \Delta G_A^0) / T \quad (4)$$

In Equation (3) $p_{s,g}$ and π_s refer to standard reference states for atmospheric and surface pressure with values of 101 kN/m² (1 atm.) and 0.338 mN/m respectively [3].

Equations (2) through (4) yield primary thermodynamic data for particular solid-vapour interactions and may be used to derive other thermodynamic quantities. Equation (5) defines the differential free energy of adsorption for a methylene group (-CH₂-) and may be derived from the primary data for a homologous series of alkanes.

$$G_A^{(CH_2)} = \Delta G_A^0(C_n H_{2n+2}) - \Delta G_A^0(C_{n-1} H_{2n}) \quad (5)$$

The adsorption of an alkane vapour onto any solid surface is due to London dispersive force attraction at the solid-vapour interface. The solid-vapour work of adhesion, w_{S-V} , is given as $G_A^{(CH_2)}$ per unit area:

$$w_{S-V} = G_A^{(CH_2)} / N \cdot a_{CH_2} \quad (6)$$

where a_{CH_2} is the area of a hypothetical (-CH₂-) group and N is Avogadro's Number.

Fowkes has shown that the work of adhesion between two phases where only dispersive interactions occur is given by:

$$W_{S-V} = 2(\gamma_S^d \gamma_L^d)^{1/2} \quad (7)$$

where γ_S^d is the dispersive component of the solid surface free energy and γ_L^d is the dispersive component of the liquid surface free energy, which for alkanes is equal to their surface tension, γ_{L-V} [5]. Thus

$$\gamma_S^d = \frac{4}{\gamma_{L-V}} \left[\frac{G_A^{(CH_2)}}{N \cdot a_{CH_2}} \right]^2 \quad (8)$$

where γ_S^d is a fundamental measure of the fibre's thermodynamic activity which is important for understanding fibre-matrix adhesion and as an indicator of fibre cleanliness.

RESULTS

Results for the samples described in Table 1 have been calculated according to Equations (1) - (4). The geometric surface area of Kevlar, $0.233 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$, was used in Equation (3). The values for q_d were obtained by a least squares fit of $\ln(V_N)$ to $1/T$. These functions were plotted to verify linearity. Figures (3) and (4) show the results for octane on each sample.

Figure 3 Plot of $\ln(V_N)$ versus $1/T$ for octane adsorption on Kevlar 49 samples 1(●), 2(X) and 3(■).

Figure 4. Plot of $\ln(V_N)$ versus $1/T$ for octane adsorption on Kevlar 29 samples 4(■), 5(●) and 6(X).

The 20 C data point for sample 5 in Figure (4) does not lie on the line passing through the data points at 30, 40 and 50 C. For this reason the hexane and heptane measurements for this sample were extended to -20 C. These results are plotted in Figure (5). Values for q_d calculated from the linear portion of these plots, ΔG_A^0 and ΔS_A^0 for Sample 1 are reported in Table (2) for each alkane vapour. Abbreviated results for the remaining samples are presented in Table (3). The γ_S^d values reported in Table (4) are based on an estimate of 0.06nm^2 for the area occupied by a methylene group, and a value of 36.2 mN/m [3] for the surface free energy of polyethylene.

TABLE 2
Complete thermodynamic analysis for Sample 1 at 30 C.

Alkane Vapour	q_d (kJ/mol)	$-\Delta G_A^0$ (kJ/mol)	$-\Delta S_A^0$ (J/mol-K)
Hexane	24.2	11.5	41.9
Heptane	28.2	14.0	47.0
Octane	32.6	16.4	53.2
Nonane	36.6	18.8	58.6
Decane	41.1	21.3	65.6

Figure 5. Plot of $\ln(V_N)$ versus $1/T$ for hexane (+), heptane (O), octane (■), nonane (X) and decane (●) on sample 5 in the range 20 to 50 C. The hexane and heptane results extend to -20 C.

TABLE 3
Abridged thermodynamic results for samples 1-6 based on octane adsorption at 30 C.

Sample	q_d (kJ/mol)	$-\Delta G_A^0$ (kJ/mol)	$-\Delta S_A^0$ (J/mol-K)
1	32.6	16.4	53.2
2	48.0	16.8	102.9
3	37.6	13.4	80.0
4	34.6	15.0	64.4
5	33.6	17.4	53.3
6	46.9	17.6	96.7

TABLE 4
Dispersive component of the fibre surface free energy, γ_S^d .

Sample Number	1	2	3	4	5	6
γ_S^d (mN/m)	33.3	54.1	36.3	35.2	37.7	55.2

DISCUSSION

The results presented in Tables (2) - (4) show clear differences amongst the various samples.

Table 4 highlights the effect of Soxhlet extraction in modifying the surface free energy of Kevlar 49 sample 2 relative to sample 1. The extraction procedure was clearly successful in removing low surface energy contaminants, leading to a 20 mN/m increase in the fibre surface free energy. While sample 1 was notionally clean by virtue of the normal production scouring process, the success of the multi-stage extraction indicates that significant improvements can be accomplished. The exact source of surface contaminants is unclear; they may be spin finishes and other processing aids, or surfactants strongly adsorbed during the scouring process.

Another important measure of the fibre-vapour interaction process is the molar entropy of adsorption, ΔS_A^0 . This is an indicator of the extent of localisation and the mobility of the adsorbed vapour molecules on the fibre surface. High negative values, as in the case of samples 2 and 6, indicate that the adsorbed vapour film is relatively localised and is confined to the surface with little molecular mobility. This would be expected for adsorption onto a solid crystalline surface. Samples 1 and 5 illustrate the opposite behaviour and the entropy values suggest significant mobility of the adsorbed vapour phase. This is consistent with the penetration of the adsorbed alkane vapour into an amorphous contaminant film.

There are major thermodynamic differences in the surface activity between the cleaned Kevlars and the as received commercially scoured materials. This implies that the surface of the scoured materials is still highly contaminated and thus the chemical activity of scoured Kevlar materials is not that of the constituent aromatic polyamide molecules.

It is known IGC is sensitive to glass and other polymeric phase transitions due to the fundamental nature of the vapour-polymer interactions [1,2]. The initial measurements of V_N between 20 and 50 C for sample 5 showed an uncharacteristic non-linearity of $\ln V_N$ versus $1/T$, compared to the other materials studied. The results between -20 and 20 C, shown in Figure 5 indicate some type of phase change in the solid adsorbate. Since it is well known that Kevlar has no phase transitions in

this temperature range, it is concluded that the phase transition takes place in a contaminant layer on the Kevlar surface. The presence of the contaminant layer on what is a commercially scoured sample is shown by the changes in surface thermodynamic properties after solvent extraction (sample 6). The conclusion that the phase change arises from this contaminant layer is supported by the lack of a similar transition in the solvent extracted material.

Application of a commercial surface finish after scouring (sample 4) resulted in the disappearance of the phase transition. This suggests that the surface finish completely covers the contaminant layer, thereby preventing it from interacting with the adsorbing vapour.

CONCLUSIONS

The results of this study demonstrate the utility of IGC as a means of characterising fibre surfaces. In particular the technique offers a means of obtaining thermodynamic information which can be useful in assessing surface contamination and chemical activity. γ_S^d and ΔS_A^0 were found to be sensitive measures of these properties. We have also found that commercially scoured Kevlar materials have significant levels of surface contamination, which may be removed by solvent extraction. The surface composition of commercially scoured Kevlar is therefore likely to be different to that of the bulk.

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